

PERMEABILITY OF FIBER REINFORCEMENTS AFTER SHEAR DEFORMATION

Chyi-Lang Lai and Wen-Bin Young

*Department of Aeronautics and Astronautics
National Cheng-Kung University
Tainan, Taiwan 70101, ROC*

SUMMARY: In liquid composite molding processes such as resin transfer molding and structural reaction injection molding, fiber reinforcements usually experience some deformation in order to conform to the complex shape of the mold cavity. Deformation of the fiber reinforcement is characterized by factors as the local surface curvature of mold and the type of reinforcements. For woven fabrics, shear deformation is the major mechanism to conform to the complicated mold cavity during the preforming process. The structure of the woven fiber mat after deformation is rearranged, resulting in variation of local fiber content. This may cause some significant effects on the fiber permeability and result in quite different mold filling pattern from expected. Incomplete wetting of the fiber preform during the mold filling stage may occur. Therefore, study of the permeabilities for deformed fiber reinforcements are quite important. In the flow simulation of the filling process, success of the prediction highly depends on the correct values of in-plane permeabilities. Change of in-plane permeability of the fabric after shear deformation must be well understood. This article investigated the permeability of woven fiber mats under different shearing angles. Several flow experiments were conducted on bidirectional woven roving fabrics in different shear angles. Two relevant factors, the ratio of principal permeabilities and the direction of principal axes with respect to the orientation of the fabric, are studied to investigate their variations with respect to shear deformation of the fiber reinforcements. It is found that the shifted angle of the principal axes is increasing with the increase of the shearing angle. At the same time, in-plane permeability ratio may decrease as increasing the shearing angle.

KEYWORDS: Permeability, resin transfer molding, polymer composites, fiber deformation

INTRODUCTION

In the fabrication of polymer composites, an important step is to homogeneously bring the polymer matrix and the fiber reinforcements together. Several manufacturing processes accomplish this step by injecting the fluid resin into the dry fiber reinforcements inside a close cavity. Among those, resin transfer molding (RTM) and structural reaction injection molding (SRIM) are becoming increasing popular composite processes because of their fast cycle time, low labor requirements and low equipment cost. In the RTM process, the pre-mixed resin is injected under pressure into a closed mold preplaced with fiber reinforcements. During this process, resin flows around and through the fiber bundles until the entire fiber reinforcements are saturated. In a reaction injection molding pultrusion (RIM pultrusion) process, resin is forced into a die to wet out the incoming dry fibers. This process differs from the traditional wet bath approach in that resin is injected into the die under a pressure. Therefore, the

pultrusion speed and the product quality are both increased. Also, the types of resin materials that can be used are less limited.

Among those processes, the most common defect encountered is the poor wetting of the fiber reinforcements, which leads to the distributions of micro-voids in the final products. The appearances of voids in the final product can be attributed to the problems of inappropriate fiber bundle wet-out and the resin filling path. Voids can appear as the resin flows unevenly and encloses air into a large dry spot or as the wetting of the fiber bundle is not complete. Researchers had conducted numerical and experimental analysis of resin filling in the RTM process in order to understand the filling flow patterns. The results can help to estimate the formation of voids due to the uneven filling flow. Permeabilities which characterize the ability of the fluid to penetrate the fiber reinforcements are the fundamental material properties used in the study of the resin filling process. Theoretical and experimental works had been conducted to study the permeabilities of different fiber reinforcements [1~36].

In the experimental measurements of the in-plane fiber permeabilities, two types of techniques were reported. For the one-dimensional case, a uniform flow from a line source is forced to penetrate through the fiber reinforcements [1~8]. The flow rate is kept constant while the injecting pressure is measured as the fluid passing through the fiber reinforcements. Based on Darcy's law, the in-plane permeabilities can be obtained from the measured injection pressure. The major drawback of this method is the leakage flow at the edges of the fiber reinforcements during the measuring process, which is called the edge effect[21, 21]. For woven fiber mats, the edge effect is more server due to the loose fiber structure near the edges. Therefore, some extra sealing at the edges of the fiber reinforcements is necessary in conducting the one-dimensional line source measurement. However, due to the difficulty of edge sealing, the repeatability of experiments using this method is quite poor. One other experimental method utilizes a two-dimensional flow [9, 10, 17]. Fluid is injected from the center of a circular fiber reinforcement and the inlet pressure and flow front positions are measured. A complicated analytical solution of the flow in a circular field is solved based on Darcy's law. Then, the measured flow front position and the inlet pressure are used to determine the permeabilities.

All of the above mentioned measurements were conducted on measuring the undeformed bi-directional and unidirectional fiber reinforcements. In liquid composite molding processes such as RTM and SRIM, fiber reinforcements usually experience some deformation in order to conform to the complex shape of the mold cavity. Deformation of the fiber reinforcement is characterized by factors as the local surface curvature of mold and the type of reinforcements. For woven fabrics, shear deformation is the major mechanism to conform to the complicated mold cavity during the preforming process. The structure of the woven fiber mat after deformation is rearranged, resulting in variation of local fiber content. This may cause some significant effects on the fiber permeability and result in quite different mold filling pattern from expected. Incomplete wetting of the fiber preform during the mold filling stage may occur. Therefore, study of the permeabilities for deformed fiber reinforcements are quite important. In the flow simulation of the filling process, success of the prediction highly depends on the correct values of in-plane permeabilities. Change of in-plane permeability of the fabric after shear deformation must be well understood.

There are few reports addressing the variation of permeability after deformation of the fiber reinforcements. Hammami [35] measured the directional permeability of unidirectional fiber mat after shear deformation. Rudd [36] reported the permeability of random and aligned fiber

mats under shear deformation. This article investigated the permeability of woven fiber mats under different deformed angles. Several flow experiments were conducted on bi-directional woven roving mats. Two relevant factors, the ratio of principal permeabilities and the direction of principal axes with respect to the orientation of the fabric, are studied to investigate their variations with respect to the shear deformation of the woven fiber mats.

Fig. 1: Description of the shearing angle and the deformed fabric

BASIC CONCEPTS

Deformation of woven fiber mat under forming process has been discussed by many researchers. The primary deformation mode is the shear deformation of the fiber roving. Fig. 1 illustrates the woven fiber roving under deformation angle θ and the resulting main axis that has an angle β with respect to the original axis. In this diagram, the warp direction is kept aligned with the original J direction, and the weft direction is sheared in an angle θ with respect to the original I direction. Due to the change of the fiber structure, the resulting principal direction of the permeability will shift to the X direction. Based on the assumption that the flow rate along the weft and warp directions are kept at the same ratio, the following relation can be devised:

$$\left(\frac{b}{a}\right)^2 \approx \alpha = \frac{k_2}{k_1} \quad (1)$$

where k_1 and k_2 are the principal permeabilities of the undeformed fiber fabric. It is further assumed that the flow front shape of the deformed fiber fabric remains elliptic. The permeability ratio ($\bar{\alpha}$) of the deformed fabric can be expressed as:

$$\bar{\alpha} = \left(\frac{Y}{X}\right)^2 = \frac{k_y}{k_x} \quad (2)$$

where k_x and k_y are the principal permeabilities of the deformed fabric. The flow front shape of the deformed fabric shown in Fig. 1 can be described by the following Equ.

$$A I^2 + B I J + J^2 + D = 0 \quad (3)$$

From Fig. 1, the ellipse passes two points, $(a\cos\theta, a\sin\theta)$ and $(0, b)$. For the undeformed fabric, the tangent of the flow front in the warp direction parallels to the weft direction, and vice versa as shown in Fig. 2. It is assumed that, for the deformed fabric, the tangent of the flow front in the warp direction still parallels to the weft direction (also shown in Fig. 2). Based on this assumption, the slope at point $(0, b)$ can be expressed as:

$$\left(\frac{dJ}{dI}\right)_b = \tan\theta \quad (4)$$

Substituting Equ 4 and the two points, $(a\cos\theta, a\sin\theta)$ and $(0, b)$, into Equ 3, the constants A , B , and D can be evaluated. The resulting Equ of the ellipse is

$$\frac{1}{\cos^2\theta} \left(\frac{b^2}{a^2} + \sin^2\theta\right) I^2 - 2\tan\theta J + J^2 - b^2 = 0 \quad (5)$$

Fig. 2: Tangent of the flow front along the weft and warp directions for deformed and undeformed fabric

By formula of the ellipse Eqs, we have

$$\tan 2\beta = \frac{B}{A-1} \quad (6)$$

and

$$\beta = \frac{1}{2} \tan^{-1} \frac{\sin 2\theta}{\cos 2\theta - \alpha} \quad (7)$$

If the ellipse Equ is described in X and Y coordinates and the relations that it passes the points $(a\cos(\beta-\theta), -a\sin(\beta-\theta))$ and $(b\sin\beta, b\cos\beta)$ are applied, the permeability ratio, $\bar{\alpha}$, is found to be

$$\bar{\alpha} = \frac{\sin^2(\beta-\theta) - \alpha \cos^2\beta}{\alpha \sin^2\beta - \cos^2(\beta-\theta)} \quad (8)$$

The above relation is based on the assumption that the tangent of the flow front along the warp direction always parallels to the weft direction. For the case of unidirectional fiber mat,

this is close to the reality since the fiber will form a barrier for the transverse flow perpendicular to the fiber. For the woven fiber fabric, the crimps of fiber roving create some vacancy between the fibers. Therefore, the weft roving only has a partial barrier effect on the flow along the warp direction. It is, thus, reasonable to modify the relation in Equ 4 to the form as:

$$\left(\frac{dJ}{dI}\right)_b = m \tan\theta \quad (9)$$

where m is a correcting factor between 0 and 1 depending the structure of the fiber network. It is assumed to be a material constant of the fiber reinforcement. The resulting ellipse equation becomes:

$$\frac{1}{\cos^2\theta} \left(\frac{b^2}{a^2} + (2m-1)\sin^2\theta \right) I^2 - 2m \tan\theta IJ + J^2 - b^2 = 0 \quad (10)$$

and

$$\beta = \frac{1}{2} \tan^{-1} \frac{m \sin 2\theta}{1 - \alpha - 2m \sin^2 \theta} \quad (11)$$

$$\bar{\alpha} = \frac{\sin^2(\beta - \theta) - \alpha \cos^2 \beta}{\alpha \sin^2 \beta - \cos^2(\beta - \theta)} \quad (12)$$

Equs 11 and 12 are used to predict the shift angle of the permeability axis and the permeability ratio for the fiber fabric that is sheared to an angle, θ . For the limit case of $\alpha = 1$, Eqs 11 and 12 become:

$$(\beta)_{\alpha=1} = \frac{\pi}{4} + \frac{\theta}{2} \quad (13)$$

$$(\bar{\alpha})_{\alpha=1} = \frac{m \sin\theta (\sin\theta - 1) + \cos^2\theta}{m \sin\theta (\sin\theta + 1) + \cos^2\theta} \quad (14)$$

As the value of m is equal to 1, Eqs 11 and 12 reduced to Eqs 7 and 8. For the case of $\beta = \theta$ (i.e., the principal permeability axis is always along the fiber roving), m has a minimum value that can be derived from Equ 11.

$$m = 1 - \alpha \quad (15)$$

Therefore, the value of m must be located in between $(1-\alpha)$ and 1 to ensure that β is always greater than θ .

EXPERIMENTAL MATERIALS AND APPARATUS

Fiberglass (E-glass) is the most commonly used reinforcement in RTM process, especially for automotive body panels. The bi-directional woven roving fiberglass mats were used in this study. A Newtonian liquid, hydraulic oil R68 with room temperature viscosity of 159 cp, was used with the woven roving fiber mat (TGFW-600 glass fiber mats from Taiwan Glass Co.,

Ltd.). The surface density of the glass fiber, which is defined as the weight per unit surface area, is equal to 600 g/m^2 .

Fig. 3: Apparatus for measuring the flow shape in deformed woven fiber mats

The flow shape in deformed fiber mats were measured using the mold filling apparatus shown schematically in Fig. 3. A pressure pot was constructed by connecting a steel cylinder to the high pressure nitrogen cylinder. The steel cylinder was filled with a non-reactive fluid by means of a gear pump and driven at a constant pressure by the high pressure source. The filling pressure can be varied by adjusting the pressure regulator.

The 30 cm by 30 cm platens of the mold were constructed from 2.5 cm thick aluminum plates. A 6.35 mm diameter inlet was drilled into the center of the lower platen. The upper platen was cut a 20 by 20 cm opening at the center, which was fitted into a hardened transparent glass. The mold cavity was formed by inserting eight pieces of rectangular 2 mm or 5 mm thick aluminum blocks between the upper and lower molds. The entire assembly was clamped together by screw bolts. Measurements were made by placing in the mold cavity with a 18x18 cm fiberglass stack containing a 1.8 cm hole in the center. The fiber reinforcements were first sheared to the desired angle and, then, cut into the size to fit in the mold. As fluid was injected from the center gate, the flow shape was recorded.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

TGFW-600 glass fiber mats were used to check the first assumption done in the previous analysis. The fiber fabric was first sheared to the desired angle, then the fluid was injected into fiber fabric. Until a developed ellipse shape was formed, the injection was stopped. The wet distances along the weft and warp roving from the inlet to the flow front were measured. Fig. 4 shows plot of the ratio, (b/a) , with respect to different shear angles. Although, the data scatters a lot, the mean value seems to keep unchanged with respect to the shear angle.

Fig. 4: Ratio (b/a) for fiber fabric with different shear angle

Fig. 5: Principal direction angle for fiber fabric with different shear angles

The principal directions of the fiber fabric after shear deformation were also measured. The image of the flow front was first scanned into the computer, then a best fit ellipse to the flow front image was found to define the principal direction. The principal direction angle for TGFW-600 glass fiber mat is plotted against the shear angles as shown in Fig. 5. It shows a gradually increase for the principal direction angle that is always larger than the corresponding shear angle. The predictions from Equs 11 and 12 are also shown in Fig. 5 with m equaling to 0.6 and 1. For this type of fiber fabric, $m = 0.6$ gives a better prediction of the principal angle. The permeability ratios for fiber fabric after deformation are shown in

Fig. 6 together with the prediction with $m=1$ and $m=0.6$. Again, the prediction for $m=0.6$ gives a better prediction.

From the experimental observation of measuring other type of fiber fabric, it could be concluded that, as α is less than 0.4, the value of m is close to $(1-\alpha)$. This is for the types of fiber reinforcements with strong flow preference in one direction than the other, such as unidirectional fiber mat. As mentioned before, for this type of fiber mats, the principal direction always follows the roving direction, and the value of m will approach its minimum. For woven roving bi-directional fiber mats, the value of m found in the laboratory is close to 0.6~0.7 for $\alpha > 0.6$. However, it is a function of α , which is unable to be defined theoretically in the current status.

Fig. 6: Permeability ratio for fiber fabric with different shear angles

CONCLUSIONS

This article investigated the permeability of woven fiber mats with shearing angles. Several flow experiments were conducted on bidirectional woven roving fabrics in different shear angles. Two relevant factors, the ratio of principal permeabilities and the direction of principal axes with respect to the orientation of the fabric, are studied to investigate their variations with respect to shear deformation of the fiber reinforcements. It is found that the shifted angle of the principal axes is increasing with the increase of the shearing angle. At the same time, in-plane permeability ratio may decrease as increasing the shearing angle. A theoretical model was proposed to predict the principal direction angle and permeability ratio after the fiber fabric was deformed.

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